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THE ROLE OF NON-STATE ACTORS IN MARITIME GOVERNANCE.

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Policy Statement

This policy brief analyses the role of non-State actors (NSAs) in maritime governance, starting from the recognition that the Ocean, by its extraterritorial and relational nature, challenges traditional models based exclusively on State sovereignty. The results show that although civil society organisations, epistemic communities, traditional populations, and private companies already perform relevant functions such as monitoring, certification, and advocacy, their role remains restricted to consultative positions, being excluded from binding decision-making processes, which generates tensions between efficiency, representativeness, and legitimacy. It is therefore recommended that the architecture of maritime governance be reformulated to effectively incorporate NSAs into international mechanisms, especially within legal and institutional frameworks, particularly those within the United Nations system, ensuring that their inclusion goes beyond symbolic participation and contributes to balancing efficiency and equity. It is concluded that building a more inclusive, equitable, and responsive ocean governance depends on a critical review of the notions of sovereignty, authority, and representation, so as to reflect not only the interests of States but also the diversity of actors who interact with the sea and take responsibility for its stewardship.

Background

The ocean is an essentially international environment. Its defining physical characteristic – its liquid surface – covers 70% of the planet's area [1], rendering it intrinsically unique. This nature, however, is ambiguous and open to subjective interpretation: through maritime routes, peoples communicate via trade and transport; yet, simultaneously, the seas separate continents and the societies inhabiting them – thus distinguishing, both culturally and geographically, the “us” from the “them”. Nevertheless, the phenomenon of globalisation – particularly from the 1990s onwards – has exerted intense pressure to narrow both the physical and metaphorical boundaries of the world in an increasingly irreversible manner. This process has, in turn, accompanied the proliferation of multilateral entities, international organizations, transnational corporations, and non-state actors of all kinds and purposes (Rosneau, 1997; Keohane & Nye, 2001). Naturally, this dynamic has also extended to the oceanic domain.

The dichotomy between “land” and “sea” is not a contemporary phenomenon but a recurring theme in international politics. Historically, geopolitical rivalries have often been shaped by the tension between land-based and maritime powers (Mahan, 1890;

Spykman, 1944; Steinberg, 2001): the naval supremacy of the Delian League (5th century BCE) contrasted with the land-based strength of the Peloponnesian League during the Greco-Persian Wars (499–449 BCE) and the Peloponnesian War (431–404 BCE); the confrontation between Athenian thalassocracy and the imperial expansion of Achaemenid Persia under Xerxes I (480 BCE); the failed attempt by the Habsburg Spanish Armada to invade England (1588), within the broader context of conflicts involving continental powers such as France (16th and 17th centuries); British maritime hegemony (after 1651, reinforced by the Navigation Acts) in contrast with the land power of Prussia under Frederick the Great (1740–1786), and later with the Weltpolitik of Imperial Germany (1890–1914); and, finally, the Cold War (1947–1991), which opposed the naval globalism of the United States to the Eurasian territorial bloc of the Soviet Union.

This analytical framework, however, privileges the actors traditionally recognised as protagonists of the international system: the States. More than a mere political division, this reflects a persistent – yet ultimately limiting – human attempt to project terrestrial worldviews onto the sea. A representative example of this is the antithetical notion of “maritime territory”. Despite collective efforts to naturalise such projections, there remains a substantial degree of aberration in the way political consciousness attempts to engage with oceanic spaces – that is, spaces devoid of territorial demarcation, permanent human habitation, imposed sovereignty, or subjection to a particular jurisdiction, and where the legitimate use of force is limited and constrained.

Parallel to the State-centric efforts to “govern” maritime spaces, civil society remains notably marginalised within formal maritime governance structures. Although the legal principle of the “common heritage of mankind” (UNCLOS, Part XI, Articles 136–149, 1986; IOC-UNESCO, 2020) theoretically aims to democratise ocean governance, its implementation remains dominated by intergovernmental institutions (such as the International Maritime Organisation, IMO, and the International Seabed Authority, ISA), which prioritise State sovereignty (De Santo et al., 2021). Civil society actors – including non-governmental organisations (NGOs), epistemic communities (Haas, 1992), fishers’ cooperatives (Jentoft, 2000), and even private maritime security companies (Bueger & Edmunds, 2017) – are often relegated to consultative roles (such as observer status in ISA meetings) or entirely excluded from binding decision-making processes (Allison, 2021). This dynamic perpetuates a hierarchy between State and non-State actors (Risse, 2012), thereby limiting alternative governance models, such as co-management by traditional and riverside communities (Chuenpagdee & Jentoft, 2018) or hybrid public–private arrangements (Cutler et al., 1999).

From this emerges a substantial question: legitimacy. In the contemporary context, does the automatic association between public authority and popular will remain plausible? Or might non-State actors – by virtue of their disassociation from direct governmental authority – become the new representatives of humanity’s collective aspirations for its common heritage? Are these actors truly free from interests other than those of an internationally organised society? The fact that such non-traditional actors have only recently been incorporated into decision-making spaces may partly explain the persistence of these unresolved questions.

Findings

Maritime Governance

Maritime governance is a concept that reflects a multifaceted phenomenon. It also bears strong correspondence with constructs such as “good order at sea”[2]. In essence, maritime governance constitutes an interagency and multi-level system of rules, institutions, and practices that regulate maritime activities, blending elements of State sovereignty, transnational regimes, and private-sector initiatives to address security, environmental, and economic challenges in ocean spaces. Thus, conceptualising “maritime governance” is intrinsically dependent on the analytical approach one chooses to prioritise in relation to ocean-related phenomena.

Maritime governance combines State sovereignty, transnational regimes, and private initiatives – yet its essence remains hierarchical. While non-State actors monitor illegal fishing (e.g., Global Fishing Watch) or certify sustainable tuna (e.g., Marine Stewardship Council), their role is consultative rather than decisional (Allison, 2021). For instance, the Marine Environment Protection Committee of the IMO includes industry NGOs (e.g., the International Chamber of Shipping), yet does not grant them voting rights (Roe, 2013).

If legitimacy stems from representation (Dahl, 1998), can a system dominated by States truly claim to govern the “common heritage” of humankind? Non-state actors – from Greenpeace to Pacific fishers – often embody oceanic interests, whether local or global, more directly than the States themselves (Bender, 2020). Still, their exclusion persists, suggesting that maritime governance is less about “good order” and more about preserving state prerogatives.

The hierarchical nature of this system reveals a central tension: non-State actors are increasingly performing governance functions – shaping norms, monitoring compliance, and filling enforcement gaps – while simultaneously being denied the authority to establish binding rules (Avant et al., 2010). For instance, the Marine Stewardship Council certifies 15% of global wild-capture fisheries (MSC, [n.d.]), yet its standards do not carry the force of international law. These non-State actors – from Indigenous fishers to epistemic communities – often express oceanic interests rooted in local contexts or planetary-scale concerns more directly than States. This asymmetry echoes Risse’s (2012) notion of “governance without empowerment”, in which non-state actors are tolerated as service providers but excluded from the core of sovereignty.

But who can legitimately “speak for the oceans”? States derive their authority from territorial sovereignty; however, their historical record includes overfishing, pollution, and a failure to meet conservation targets (IPCC, 2019). In contrast, non-State actors – from Indigenous fishers to scientific coalitions – often represent oceanic interests at both local and global levels (Steinberg, 2001). Their legitimacy may stem from expertise (Haas, 1992), moral advocacy (Allison, 2021), or democratic claims to represent “global civil society” (Dingwerth, 2007). However, these sources of legitimacy remain contested, as non-state actors lack electoral mandates and universal accountability mechanisms.

Recommendations

Civil Representativeness and State Sovereignty

The inclusion of non-State actors in decision-making processes raises concerns about the potential dilution of State sovereignty, yet their exclusion perpetuates governance gaps. In this regard, the international system tends to preserve political architectures that favour the path of sovereignty. However, problems arise when considering the State’s dual function as both regulator and regulated. For example, the overexploitation of fish stocks occurs not only due to the prioritisation of short-term economic interests by States, but also due to their inaction or inefficacy in developing means to curb overfishing – or even to provide data for the sustainable management of these resources. In this domain, for instance, no civil society organisations possess, beyond advocacy roles, the actual capacity to partake in sanctioning processes against predatory and/or irregular fishing fleets.

The legitimacy of non-State actors, moreover, rests on alternative paradigms, such as epistemic communities, whose credibility is grounded in expertise (Haas, 1992); social movements, such as environmentalism, which are guided by a form of “moral authority”; and native and Indigenous populations, historically recognised as stewards of ecosystems (Chuenpagdee & Jentoft, 2018). Unlike States, however, these forms of legitimacy lack institutionalised mechanisms of oversight and accountability, raising concerns regarding democratic control.

The inclusion of non-State actors may, nonetheless, enhance the efficiency of governance. This prompts debates concerning efficiency versus equity. For example, private maritime security companies proved effective in reducing piracy rates off the coast of Somalia, to levels comparable to those achieved by traditional military forces (Bueger & Edmunds, 2017). However, a critical and goal-oriented approach must guide the adoption of such public policies, to avoid mere “inclusion for inclusion’s sake”. In the case of private military companies performing constabulary maritime security roles, their profit-driven objectives tend to favour commercial interests to the detriment of community ones – as seen in the exclusion of artisanal fishers from patrolled zones. Therefore, the integration of non-State actors should serve to enhance the means of effectiveness in maritime governance, not to be a self-centred end.

Building a more representative and plural architecture of maritime governance – whether at local, regional, or global levels – through the inclusion of non-State actors ultimately entails a revision of the legal mechanisms that regulate human activities in the Ocean. Paradoxically, such a revision must take place within the realm of international law, which remains an exclusive domain of States as subjects of public law. Some of these legal instruments, in contrast, tend towards weakening the sovereignty of the very same States. The principle of the “common heritage of humankind”^[3] (UNCLOS, 1982; UNESCO, 2020) is a notable example. If the Ocean indeed belongs to humanity, then non-State actors – as representatives of diffuse global interests – should be entitled to more than mere consultative roles. However, granting them voting power within bodies such as the International Seabed Authority (ISA) would require a reconfiguration of the very foundations of international law (De Santo et al., 2021), since “Neptune” did not sign the United Nations Charter.

Final Considerations

This paper has demonstrated that maritime governance can no longer be understood solely through traditional State-based models, nor by approaches centred exclusively on the logic of national sovereignty. The multiplicity of actors involved in oceanic dynamics necessitates a revision of conventional analytical frameworks, particularly those that have historically overlooked the fluidity, extraterritoriality, and relational nature of maritime spaces. Critical and constructivist approaches – by emphasising the intersubjectivity of actors and the plurality of rationalities involved – reveal that the sea is not merely a zone of geopolitical contestation. Still, also a space where power practices, forms of knowledge, and struggles for legitimacy are deeply intertwined.

In this regard, the existing normative and institutional structure remains under strain, as it continues to privilege the protagonism of State entities, even in the face of increasingly complex global oceanic challenges. The idea of the “common heritage of humankind”, though enshrined in law, remains limited in its implementation, as it is subordinated to the logic of national interest and the centrality of intergovernmental institutions. Non-State actors remain, for the most part, relegated to peripheral or consultative roles, despite often possessing superior technical expertise, territorial reach, and sociopolitical legitimacy compared to many States in specific contexts. This institutionalised exclusion represents a barrier to the development of more inclusive, equitable, and responsive models of ocean governance.

Thus, recognising the role of non-State actors is not merely a matter of expanding the analytical scope, but of promoting substantive transformations in the architecture of maritime governance. The effective incorporation of these actors into decision-making processes – particularly traditional communities, epistemic organisations, and transnational environmental monitoring and advocacy networks – demands a reconfiguration of the notions of authority, sovereignty, and representation. The debate must move beyond mere service provision or symbolic participation towards a model in which legitimacy derives from a plurality of voices and the capacity to respond to contemporary ecological and social urgencies. In the end, if the Ocean belongs to all of humanity, its governance must reflect not only the interests of States, but the diversity of actors who interact with it, depend upon it, and take responsibility for its stewardship.

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[1] See NOAA – National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. How much of the Earth is water? National Ocean Service, 2021. Available at: <<https://oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts/oceanwater.html>>. Accessed May 25th, 2025.

[2] Cf. United Nations General Assembly (UNGA). A/RES/63/63 (March 2008). Available at: <<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/628433?v=pdf>>. Accessed May 2025.

[3] Emphasis added.

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